

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Dissemination material

Deliverable No.	D1.4		
Due Date	31.03.2017		
Submission Date	02.04.2018		
Deliverable Leader	SUPSI / UOM / IST / UGM		
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	PP	Restricted to other project participants (including R4D services)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
Status	to be continuously updated		

Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
0.1	20-02-2017	Daniele Strigaro	Document creation
0.2	31-03-2017	Daniele Strigaro	Content added
1.0	09-05-2018	Daniele Strigaro	Content updated

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
0.1	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro
0.2	SUPSI	Daniele Strigaro, Massimiliano Cannata
1.0	SUPSI / UOM	Daniele Strigaro, Massimiliano Cannata, Emeshi Warusavitharana

NOTES:

For comments / suggestions / contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4nse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch

For more information on the project 4nse, link to <http://www.4nse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

Contents

Executive summary 4

1 Brochure..... 4

2 Banner 4

3 Poster..... 5

4 Sticker 6

Executive summary

This report includes the dissemination material produced to publicize the 4onse project among its stakeholders during the period of 01st October 2016 to 30th April 2018..

1 Brochure

Date	Location	Picture	Annex
21 November 2016	Hotel Ozo, Colombo, Sri Lanka	<p>The image shows a brochure with the following content:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PROJECT PARTNERS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland - Coordinator University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka - Partner Institute of Space Technology, Pakistan - Partner University of Gadjah Mada, Indonesia - Partner International of Water Management Institute, Sri Lanka - Collaboration Irrigation Department, Sri Lanka - Collaboration Global Facility for Disaster Reduction & Recovery (GFDRR) USA - Collaboration FOR FURTHER INFORMATION, CONTACT: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prof. Massimiliano Casatta: massimiliano.casatta@supsi.ch Dr. Rangajewee Rathnayaka: rangajewee@ion.lk Tel / Fax: +94 (1) 2650923 Website: www.4onse.org 4onse logo and tagline: "4 times open & non-conventional technology for sensing the environment" Logos of partners: FN-NF (Swiss National Science Foundation), Swiss Programme for Research on Global Issues in Development, Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft, and SDC (Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation). 	B01

2 Banner

Date	Location	Picture	Annex
21 November 2016	Hotel Ozo, Colombo, Sri Lanka	<p>The image shows a banner with the following text:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 times open & non-conventional technology for sensing the environment 4ONSE අලුත් පරිසර හඳුනා ගැනීමේ තාක්ෂණය 	n.a.

3 Poster

Date	Location	Picture	Annex
<p>26 January 2018</p>	<p>SUPSI, Canobbio, Switzerland</p>	<p>University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland Department for Environment, Constructions and Design Institute of Earth Sciences</p> <p>SUPSI 4nse: analysis of Open, Non-conventional, Sustainable and Effective monitoring systems</p> <p>The problem Environmental Monitoring Systems are essential to observe hydro-meteorological parameters used for the mitigation of natural disasters, the water management and the weather forecasting. However, in developing and low income countries, the lack of affordable, dense and modern monitoring systems due to high costs of hardware and software components, low access to replacement parts and limited local capacity. In addition, conventional systems are usually characterized by low interoperability and scarce metadata, mainly because of the closed and proprietary nature of the components.</p> <p>The project The 4nse project studies non-conventional monitoring systems fully based on open technologies for the management of resources and natural hazards in developing countries. After the design of the system, the study involves the installation of 30 stations in a Sri Lankan basin and the set-up of management and warning systems for floods and droughts. The system will be analyzed to fully understand the real cost of ownership, data quality and applicability in real situations. If properly validated, these systems can provide an alternative disruptive solution to support goods and lives protection.</p> <p>The result The project goal is strengthening data production and management for sustainable development in low income economies. To this end, the project impacts the capability of developing countries in managing and evaluating monitoring systems. In fact, if scientifically verified and validated, such a kind of fully accessible, royalty-free and low cost system, could potentially enable developing countries in managing natural resources and hazards thanks to better reaction time, improved understanding, faster decision making and more effective policies implementations.</p> <p>Contact Information Massimiliano Carnata massimiliano.carnata@supsi.ch</p> <p>Funding agency The project is part of the Swiss Programme for Research on Global Issues for Development (PRG) programme, which is a joint funding initiative by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) and the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF).</p> <p>Partner Institute of Earth Sciences, SUPSI, Canobbio (CH) University of Moratuwa, UDM, Colombo (SL) Institute of Space Technology, IST, Bhubaneswar (IN)</p> <p>Research domain AI, Built environment, natural resources and safety</p>	<p>P01</p>
<p>28 October 2017</p>	<p>Forum innovazione, Lugano, Switzerland</p>	<p>University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland</p> <p>SUPSI²⁰</p> <p>4nse: analysis of Open, Non-conventional, Sustainable and Effective monitoring systems Low-cost and open monitoring system to manage water resources and hydrological hazards in the low-income and developing countries.</p>	<p>n.a.</p>

<p>24 March 2017</p>	<p>University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka</p>		<p>n.a.</p>
----------------------	--	--	-------------

4 Sticker

Description	Picture	Annex
<p>Template to build 4onse station's sticker</p>	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>4 times open & non-conventional technology for sensing the environment</p> <p>Research project on setting-up OPEN WEATHER STATIONS as a fully accessible, royalty-free and low cost Environment Monitoring System (EMS) based on open hardware, software, data and standards.</p> <p>Research Project by:</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana Dipartimento ambiente costruzioni e design Istituto scienze della Terra</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>UNIVERSITY OF MORATUWA SRI LANKA</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Institute of Space Technology Islamabad, Pakistan</p> </div> </div> <p>Funded by:</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft Confédération suisse Confederazione Svizzera Confederaziun svizra</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION</p> </div> </div> </div> <div style="width: 45%; border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p>Contact and information:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">www.4onse.ch</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p>Institute of Earth Sciences Campus Trevano, Via Trevano CH-6952 Canobbio T +41 (0) 58 666 62 00 F +41 (0) 58 666 62 09 ist@supsi.ch</p> <p>Prof. Massimiliano Cannata massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch</p> </div> </div>	<p>S01</p>